

Traditional and Cooperative Learning Approaches in Teaching Filipino 9-Asian Literature

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Abstract

This research revolves on the use of traditional and Cooperative Learning methods in teaching Filipino 9 - Asian Literature at Zamboanguita Science High School. It aims to determine the effectiveness of these mentioned methods on students' learning in the Filipino subject. The research underwent Methodological Triangulation with pre-test and post-test, actual classroom observation, and Focus Group Discussion. The respondents were twenty-nine (29) students in the experimental group and twenty-eight (28) students in the control group. The study found no significant difference between the pretest results of the lessons of the respondents in both groups. However, there was a significant difference between the post-test results of the respondents' lessons. It was found that before the introduction of the Cooperative Learning method to the experimental group, the level of knowledge of the respondents from both groups was not far apart. It was also shown that the use of the Cooperative Learning method cannot be applied to all lessons. There are only specific lessons where this method is effective.

Keywords: Cooperative Learning, Traditional Method, Methodological Triangulation, pretest, posttest, lecture, Ask Together Learn Together, control group, experimental group

Introduction

Under the 1987 Constitution of the Philippines, Section 1, it was clearly stated that the teaching of literature is anchored in a mandate and rationale. Literature is one of the fields of Filipino subject and is part of the Philippine Education Curriculum wherein it was being stressed that all the citizens especially the Philippine learners must be given an opportunity to become an individual who is good in all aspects of life.

On the other hand, the Board of National Education also strengthened the importance of teaching literature with the goal that must be followed and implemented by all schools in the country. It was also being highlighted that the instruction of literature is part of the 8th objective which states

"To promote the sciences, arts and letters for the enrichment of life and recognition of the dignity of human person."

Furthermore, they also stressed out that arts and literature encourage the learners to see the beauty and reality in any forms. On the contrary, the instruction of literature in Philippine educational setting is facing a dilemma and is the exact opposite of the mentioned goals and rationale. The sole roles of learners during instruction is to read and to understand the content of the specific literature and to answer the guide questions. The learners were no longer encouraged to see importance and beauty of literature and the opportunity of learning in an interesting manner was compromised.

In connection to the mentioned situation, it was being observed that the teaching of literature focused only on the transfer of knowledge from the teacher to the learners through a strategy that has been used to over the past years which led to students having a low-level class participation. The use of non-traditional teaching strategy during the teaching-learning process might not be an easy step for some teachers due to the fear of integrating change in the teaching process and hesitation of embracing such new strategy.

At present, Cooperative Learning is seen as one of the teaching strategies that promotes effectivity in instruction. According to Dahley (1994), cooperative learning is an instructional strategy wherein students work together in small groups to attain the specific objective. Traditional strategy, on the other hand, happens under the supervision and control of teachers (Richards, 2008).

Based on the above-mentioned scenario, the researcher was encouraged to conduct a study to identify the efficacy of the non-traditional strategy (cooperative learning) and the traditional strategy (lecture) in teaching literature in Zamboanguita Science High School particularly in Filipino 9 - Asian Literature in the learners' learning process.

Literature Review

This research is grounded in the Cooperative Learning theory proposed by D. Johnson and R. Johnson (1998), which is rooted in three main theoretical perspectives: Social Interdependence Perspective, Cognitive Developmental

Perspective, and Behavioral-Social Perspective. Additionally, it incorporates the Traditional Approaches to teaching literature—namely, the Information-based Approach, Paraphrastic Approach, and Moral Philosophical Approach as outlined by Carter and Long (1991).

Cooperative learning is an instructional approach where students collaborate in small groups to assist each other in the learning process, working towards a shared goal (Acikgoz,2003). As defined by D. Johnson, R. Johnson (2003), and Holubec, this method entails students collectively working to achieve group objectives that are unattainable when working alone or in a competitive setting.

The components and conditions necessary for a group activity to qualify as a cooperative learning process, as outlined by D. Johnson and R. Johnson (2003), include positive interdependence, individual accountability, face-to-face interaction, social skills, and group processing. Positive interdependence is achieved when all group members appreciate and understand the importance of cooperation to reach the group's objectives. Face-to-face interaction encourages group members to work harder towards the group's success. In the cooperative learning model, the group functions as a unified entity, with its overall success or failure reliant on the contributions of each member.

Social Interdependence Perspective

According to D. Johnson, R. Johnson, and Holubec E. (1998), interaction is crucial for what is known as human survival. However, in the context of education, social interdependence refers to the overall perseverance and efforts of students to achieve and develop positive relationships, psychological adjustment, and to demonstrate social competence. The theory suggests that the framework of social interdependence shapes how individuals engage with each other. Consequently, a key cooperative element required in the classroom is positive interdependence or collaboration. Such cooperation leads to promotive interaction, where members consistently motivate each other to learn and engage in activities.

Cognitive-Developmental Perspective

The cognitive developmental perspective draws from the theories of Jean Piaget and Lev Vygotsky (D. Johnson, R. Johnson, and Holubec E., 1998). According to Piaget's viewpoint, socio-cognitive conflict and cognitive disequilibrium emerge when people work together on a task. These conflicts and disequilibria occur when individuals face new situations and information that do not fit their current understanding, prompting them to engage in discussions and reasoning with peers to acquire knowledge. This process aids in the development of cognitive problem-solving skills.

Behavioral-Social Perspective

Johnson and R. Johnson (2000) explained that the cooperation and efforts of each group member are driven by extrinsic motivation to achieve group rewards. Extrinsic rewards are highly motivating for students as they work together as a group. This focuses on the impact of reinforcing cooperation among group members and the group reward when learning occurs. B.F. Skinner's (2001) study, on the other hand, focused on the opportunity to be part of a group that values its current members. Bandura's (2001) study concentrated on modeling, meaning that the group receiving the reward becomes a model for other groups aiming to receive rewards as well. Bandura's study emphasizes observation and modeling.

The behavioral-social perspective can be linked to the concept of the motivationalist perspective because both focus on rewards or incentives that motivate students to perform a task or activity. From the motivationalist perspective, the goal structure in the concept of cooperation creates a situation where each group member can achieve their personal goals only if their group succeeds, meaning that the group's success is each member's success (D. Johnson and R. Johnson 1998; Slavin,1993).

Information-based Approach

Carter (1998) considers this approach as a method of teaching knowledge about literature, where it is viewed as a source of information for students. Lazar (1993) emphasized that this approach is teacher-centered and its concept focuses on the content of the literature itself. It requires extensive input from the teacher for students to effectively analyze the history and characteristics of literary movements arising from cultural, social, political, and historical backgrounds towards the work or text (Sii & Chen, 2016). This approach involves reading criticisms, notes, explanations, and lectures provided by the teacher in preparation for an examination.

Moral-Philosophical Approach

This approach incorporates moral values in the teaching of literature. According to Carter & Long (1991), this approach facilitates the acquisition of knowledge about the author's life, cultural practices, and the historical scope of literature through the teacher's thorough discussion of its content. In this way, students learn both the literature

and the culture associated with it. This approach also helps students understand the moral and philosophical values contained in literature. Additionally, students achieve self-realization and self-understanding while interpreting a literary work with the teacher's guidance.

Paraphrastic Approach

This approach is considered teacher-centered as it focuses on the teacher's role in re-reading the text using simple language before learning and interpretation take place. According to Carter (1998), this approach involves students interpreting the text they read with the help of the teacher. The success of students in interpretation depends on how the teacher simplifies the deep statements within the text. The method used by the teacher in this approach is paraphrasing or re-wording using simple language to make the ideas conveyed by the text, which initially caused confusion, clear to the students.

Therefore, this approach starts with (1) reading the text in its original language, (2) re-reading the text using simpler language or re-telling the text using simpler language, (3) using translation with the mother tongue or first language, (4) reading the text using paraphrased versions prepared by the teacher or found in workbooks, (5) individual activities, and (6) exams.

Overall, in the traditional method, the information-based approach involves teaching literature through reading criticisms, notes, explanations, and lectures provided by the teacher. The moral-philosophical approach focuses on acquiring knowledge about the author's life, cultural practices, and the historical scope of literature through the teacher's thorough discussion of the literary content. Meanwhile, the paraphrastic approach centers on the teacher's role in re-reading the text using simple language before learning and interpretation take place.

Methodology

This section explains the research design, participants, instrument used, data collection methods, and ethical considerations of the study.

Research Design

The research design is a quasi-experimental pre-test-post-test model aimed at measuring scores before and after introducing the treatment to both experimental and control groups. To ensure internal validity, performance levels were measured before and after changes were introduced. According to Campbell and Stanley (1963 in Abbott, 2005), the simplest design is: Group 1: Pretest – Treatment – Posttest Group 2: Pretest – Posttest
This study follows that model:

Experimental group: Pretest – Cooperative Learning – Posttest

Control group: Pretest – Traditional – Posttest

Both groups were given pretests and posttests at the same intervals, with the pre-test before the lesson and the post-test after. Performance was analyzed using the T-test for significance. The questions aimed to achieve the same objectives, ensuring validity.

Research Participants

In this study, the researcher conducted the teaching in the selected sections. Among the six sections taught by the researcher at Zamboanguita Science High School, the two sections involved in the study were chosen: grade 9-Venido and grade 9-Verances, because the school only has two sections for grade 9 and the study focused on Filipino 9 – Asian Literature. Additionally, the researcher selected the respondents based on their level of cooperation and sense of responsibility. According to the researcher's observation, especially during class, grade 9 students demonstrated more cooperation compared to the lower grades. Furthermore, the grade 9 students were more responsible and showed higher interest in carrying out tasks.

The selection of respondents for the experimental and control groups was done randomly as the respondents had similar levels of knowledge and their grades were not significantly different due to the school's cut-off grade policy at Zamboanguita Science High School.

Research Instrument & Method

This study utilized methodological triangulation in data collection. The first method was the teacher-made test, including pre-test and post-test, which were both multiple choice, giving respondents only fifteen minutes to complete. However, before using the pre-test and post-test with the respondents, the researcher conducted pilot testing at Sibulan Science High School. Twenty-three (23) ninth-grade students from the said school participated in the pilot testing. To determine the quality and effectiveness of the test items, the teacher-made pre-test and post-test were subjected to an item discrimination index by the researcher.

The formula used is: **Discrimination Index** = $\frac{U_p - L_p}{L}$
wherein:

U_p = number of high performers who got question right

L_p = number of low performers who got question right

U = number of high performers

L = number of low performers

Or this formula:

$$D_i = C_{UG} - C_{LG} / D$$

wherein:

D_i = discrimination index value

C_{UG} = number of students selecting the correct answer in the upper group

C_{LG} = number of students selecting the correct answer in the lower group

The table below shows the evaluation given for the results obtained from the item discrimination index.

Discrimination Index	Item Evaluation
.40 and above	Very good items
.30 - .39	Reasonably good items, but possibly subject to improvement
.20 - .29	Marginal items, usually needing improvement
.19 and below	Poor items, to be rejected or improved by revision

Guidelines for Evaluating the Discriminating Efficiency of Items

The second method of data collection was video recording (actual class observation of the experimental and control groups) aimed at capturing the activities within the two groups.

Focus group discussions were also conducted with both groups to gather data about the respondents' classroom experiences using the teacher's teaching methods. An equal number of respondents participated in the focus group discussions, with ten (10) respondents from the experimental group and ten (10) from the control group. Two meetings were allocated to explain information about the Ask Together - Learn Together strategy using the cooperative learning method to the experimental group, and similarly, the presentational mode using the traditional lecture method to the control group. Initially, the researcher administered the pre-test at the beginning of the discussion for both the experimental and control groups. After the pre-test, the lessons were conducted, and following each lesson, a post-test was given as the final test.

Data Gathering Procedures

Before commencing the study, the researcher obtained permission from the Schools Division Superintendent of Negros Oriental and the school head of Zamboangita Science High School through a letter. This study employed a quasi-experimental pre-test-post-test design. Both groups of respondents took a pre-test before the treatment was administered and a post-test afterward. To ensure the quality and effectiveness of the test items, pilot testing was conducted, and the items were evaluated using an item discrimination index.

The study involved two sections from Grade 9 of Zamboangita Science High School, with the researcher personally overseeing both sections. The experimental group consisted of 29 respondents, and the control group had 28 respondents, all studying Filipino 9 - Asian Literature. To maintain consistent teaching quality, both groups were taught the same lessons on Asian Literature using identical lesson plans and learning objectives. The primary difference lay in the teaching strategies: the experimental group used cooperative learning, while the control group used traditional lecture methods. In the experimental group, respondents completed lessons through positive interdependence and individual accountability, whereas in the control group, the teacher played an active role in knowledge transfer.

Ethical Consideration

During the study, the researcher ensured confidentiality and followed ethical procedures. The researcher wrote a letter to the parents of the participants in order to secure permission to conduct tests (pre-test and post-test), video record actual classes, and conduct focus group discussions. It was assured that the participation of students will not affect their academic performance or grades for the two succeeding quarters. All collected data and responses will be handled confidentially and objectively. All discussions between the moderator and the participants will not be disclosed or shared with others. The participants' responses will remain confidential and will not be used for the personal purposes of the researcher.

An hour was allocated in two meetings to discuss the importance of cooperative learning in various skills that students need to achieve (social, leadership, and basic group skills and the expectations from them) throughout the grading

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period. Students were also explained how to implement Ask Together-Learn Together and were provided information about the format for completing their lessons in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature.

Emphasis was also placed on recognizing group size, forming student groups, working collaboratively within groups, individual testing, and classroom arrangement. These aspects were implemented during discussions and activities using the cooperative learning method.

Results

Tables 1 and 2 present the performance or scores in the pretest and posttest of five lessons for the respondents from the experimental group, which consists of twenty-nine (29) respondents in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature at Zamboanguita Science High School.

Table 1

Performances in the Pretest of Respondents in the Experimental Group for Quarter 1

Quarter 1	LESSON/POINTS (Pretest)									
	Lesson 1 Short Story (Singapore)		Lesson 2 Novel (Saudi Arabia)		Lesson 3 Poem (Pilipinas)		Lesson 4 Essay (Indonesia)		Lesson 5 Play (Philippines)	
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	4	1	5	2	6	1	4	1	7	1
	5	1	6	1	8	6	6	1	8	5
	6	4	7	3	9	1	7	2	9	4
	7	3	8	2	10	5	8	4	10	2
	8	4	9	5	11	6	9	3	11	4
	9	5	10	4	12	5	10	3	12	7
	10	6	11	3	13	2	11	5	13	4
	11	2	12	2	14	1	12	4	14	1
	12	3	13	2	15	1	13	2	15	1
			14	2	16	1	14	2		
			15	2			15	1		
			17	1						
	Total no. of items	29		29		29		29		29
No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
Highest Score/Mark	12		17		16		15		15	
Lowest Score/Mark	4		5		6		4		7	
Mean Score	8.59		10.21		10.69		10.24		10.76	

Table 2

Performances in the Posttest of Respondents in the Experimental Group for Quarter 1

Quarter 2	LESSON/POINTS (Posttest)										
	Lesson 1 Short Story (Singapore)		Lesson 2 Novel (Saudi Arabia)		Lesson 3 Poem (Pilipinas)		Lesson 4 Essay (Indonesia)		Lesson 5 Play (Philippines)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	7	1	11	2	6	2	7	2	11	4	
	8	4	13	2	7	1	8	1	12	3	
	9	4	14	2	8	1	9	4	13	6	
	11	5	15	5	9	1	10	1	14	4	
	12	4	16	4	10	8	11	2	15	5	
	13	2	17	8	11	4	12	6	16	6	
	14	4	18	3	12	5	13	6	19	1	
	15	5	19	3	13	4	14	4			
					14	1	15	2			
					15	2	16	1			
	Total no. of items	29		29		29		29		29	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
	Highest Score/Mark	15		19		15		16		19	
Lowest Score/Mark	7		11		6		7		11		
Mean Score	11.55		15.93		10.90		11.79		13.93		

Meanwhile, Tables 3 and 4 present the performance or scores in the pretest and posttest of five lessons for the respondents from the control group, which consists of twenty-eight (28) respondents in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature at Zamboanguita Science High School. The results of the exams show the knowledge acquired by the respondents from the experimental and control groups in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature.

Table 3

Performances in the Pretest of Respondents in the Control Group for Quarter 1

Quarter 1	LESSON/POINTS (Pretest)										
	Lesson 1 Short Story (Singapore)		Lesson 2 Novel (Saudi Arabia)		Lesson 3 Poem (Pilipinas)		Lesson 4 Essay (Indonesia)		Lesson 5 Play (Philippines)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	5	1	2	1	5	3	6	1	4	1	
	6	6	3	3	6	1	7	1	6	4	
	7	5	5	3	7	3	8	2	7	1	
	8	5	6	4	8	1	9	3	8	3	
	9	3	7	1	9	6	10	2	9	2	
	10	4	9	3	10	5	11	8	10	3	
	11	4	10	3	11	5	12	5	11	7	
			11	3	12	2	13	3	12	3	
			12	2	13	1	14	1	13	2	
			13	3	15	1	15	1	16	2	
			14	2			16	1			
	Total no. of items	28		28		28		28		28	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
Highest Score/Mark	11		14		15		16		16		
Lowest Score/Mark	5		2		5		6		4		
Mean Score	8.11		8.50		9.32		11		9.93		

Table 4

Performances in the Posttest of Respondents in the Control Group for Quarter 1

Quarter 1	LESSON/POINTS (Posttest)										
	Lesson 1 Short Story (Singapore)		Lesson 2 Novel (Saudi Arabia)		Lesson 3 Poem (Pilipinas)		Lesson 4 Essay (Indonesia)		Lesson 5 Play (Philippines)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	7	3	9	1	7	2	9	2	6	1	
	8	2	10	1	8	3	10	2	7	1	
	9	5	11	1	9	5	11	6	9	4	
	10	10	12	1	10	5	12	5	10	4	
	11	4	13	6	11	6	13	4	11	2	
	12	1	14	5	12	4	14	4	12	5	
	13	2	15	6	13	2	15	3	13	4	
	15	1	16	1	14	1	16	2	14	5	
			17	3					15	1	
			18	3					16	1	
	Total no. of items	28		28		28		28		28	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
	Highest Score/Mark	15		18		14		16		16	
Lowest Score/Mark	7		9		7		9		6		
Mean Score	9.96		14.32		10.25		12.46		11.57		

Tables 5 and 6 present the performance or scores in the pretest and posttest of five lessons for the respondents from the experimental group, which consists of twenty-nine (29) respondents in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature at Zamboanguita Science High School.

Table 5

Performances in the Pretest of Respondents in the Experimental Group for Quarter 2

Quarter 2	LESSON/POINTS (Pretest)										
	Lesson 1 Tanka & Haiku (Japan)		Lesson 2 Fable (Korea)		Lesson 3 Essay (Taiwan)		Lesson 4 Short Story (China)		Lesson 5 Play (Mongolia)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	3	2	4	2	3	1	6	1	4	1	
	6	2	5	1	6	2	8	1	9	2	
	7	5	6	2	7	8	9	4	10	3	
	9	5	8	3	8	2	10	5	11	4	
	10	2	9	2	9	4	11	5	12	8	
	11	9	10	2	10	3	12	5	13	3	
	12	4	11	6	11	4	13	4	14	1	
			12	4	12	1	14	4	15	4	
			13	2	13	1			16	2	
			14	2	14	2			18	1	
			16	2	15	1					
			17	1							
	Total no. of items	29		29		29		29		29	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
	Highest Score/Mark	12		17		15		14		18	
	Lowest Score/Mark	3		4		3		6		4	
	Mean Score	9.14		10.48		9.14		11.14		12.24	

Table 6

Performances in the Posttest of Respondents in the Experimental Group for Quarter 2

Quarter 2	LESSON/POINTS (Posttest)										
	Lesson 1 Tanka & Haiku (Japan)		Lesson 2 Fable (Korea)		Lesson 3 Essay (Taiwan)		Lesson 4 Short Story (China)		Lesson 5 Play (Mongolia)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	6	1	6	1	6	1	10	1	9	1	
	8	3	9	1	7	4	11	3	10	1	
	9	5	10	1	8	4	12	3	11	1	
	10	1	11	1	9	2	13	7	13	1	
	11	10	12	3	10	4	14	2	14	4	
	12	3	13	4	11	4	15	5	15	4	
	13	4	15	4	12	3	16	6	16	4	
	14	2	16	3	13	3	17	1	17	7	
			17	5	14	2	18	1	18	5	
			18	3	15	1			19	1	
			19	3	16	1					
	Total no. of items	29		29		29		29		29	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
	Highest Score/Mark	14		19		16		18		19	
	Lowest Score/Mark	6		6		6		10		9	
	Mean Score	10.72		14.76		10.41		13.93		15.55	

Meanwhile, Tables 7 and 8 present the performance or scores in the pretest and posttest of five lessons for the respondents from the control group, which consists of twenty-eight (28) students in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature at Zamboanguita Science High School. The results of the exams show the knowledge acquired by the respondents from the experimental and control groups in Filipino 9 – Asian Literature.

Table 7

Performances in the Pretest of Respondents in the Control Group for Quarter 2

Quarter 2	LESSON/POINTS (Pretest)										
	Lesson 1 Tanka & Haiku (Japan)		Lesson 2 Fable (Korea)		Lesson 3 Essay (Taiwan)		Lesson 4 Short Story (China)		Lesson 5 Play (Mongolia)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	5	3	3	1	5	2	6	1	5	1	
	6	3	4	1	6	2	7	1	9	3	
	7	1	5	3	7	3	8	5	10	4	
	8	8	6	2	8	3	9	3	11	8	
	9	4	7	5	9	8	10	3	12	1	
	10	5	8	1	10	3	11	6	13	5	
	11	1	9	2	11	4	12	2	14	1	
	12	3	10	4	12	2	13	2	15	3	
			11	3	13	1	14	2	16	2	
			12	4			15	1			
			13	2			16	1			
							17	1			
	Total no. of items	28		28		28		28		28	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
	Highest Score/Mark	12		13		13		17		16	
	Lowest Score/Mark	5		3		5		6		5	
	Mean Score	8.46		7.79		8.93		10.79		11.71	

Table 8

Performances in the Posttest of Respondents in the Control Group for Quarter 2

Quarter 2	LESSON/POINTS (Posttest)										
	Lesson 1 Tanka & Haiku (Japan)		Lesson 2 Fable (Korea)		Lesson 3 Essay (Taiwan)		Lesson 4 Short Story (China)		Lesson 5 Play (Mongolia)		
	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	score	f	
lowest mark ↓ highest mark	6	1	7	2	6	1	8	1	8	1	
	8	4	8	1	7	2	9	2	10	2	
	9	1	9	2	8	6	10	3	11	2	
	10	4	10	1	9	4	11	1	12	3	
	11	5	11	5	10	5	12	7	13	7	
	12	5	12	2	11	6	13	5	14	4	
	13	5	13	4	12	1	14	7	15	4	
	14	1	14	5	13	1	15	1	16	1	
			1	15	4	14	1	16	1	17	1
			16	1	15	1			18	2	
			18	1					19	1	
	Total no. of items	28		28		28		28		28	
	No. of items	20		20		20		20		20	
	Highest Score/Mark	18		18		15		16		19	
	Lowest Score/Mark	6		7		6		8		8	
	Mean Score	11.25		12.32		9.79		12.32		13.61	

Roles Played and Contributions of These Roles to the Success of Discussions Among Respondents in the Experimental and Controlled Groups

Based on the roles played by the respondents, it was shown that respondents in the experimental group actively and enthusiastically participated in the learning process, while respondents in the controlled group were merely recipients of information, and their participation in discussions could be considered passive.

The study also revealed that the contributions of the roles played by respondents were not identical in making the discussions successful. In the experimental group, various roles were played by the respondents, resulting in diverse contributions. Meanwhile, in the controlled group, being listeners, receivers, and recorders of information helped them understand the topic more easily and answer the teacher's questions.

Reasons Why the Methods Used in Teaching Filipino 9 - Asian Literature are Effective

The study also showed that the modern method (cooperative learning) used by the teacher was effective for the respondents in the experimental group, including the sharing of knowledge gained from other groups. Meanwhile, in the controlled group, the use of the traditional method (lecture) by the teacher was also effective, particularly in enhancing the respondents' listening skills.

Materials that Assisted and Will Assist the Learning of Respondents in both Groups

This study highlighted various materials used in each method that aided the learning of respondents in both the experimental and controlled groups. It was found that the use of technology, such as television, laptops, and PowerPoint presentations, benefited both groups. Additionally, based on the interviews conducted with the respondents, those in the control group expressed a desire for the teacher to use visual aids. If a story is to be discussed, they suggested showing moving pictures and animations to better understand the topic.

Reasons for Respondents' Appreciation of the Teaching Method for Filipino 9 – Asian Literature

The study indicated that both the experimental and control groups appreciated the teacher's approach to teaching Filipino 9 – Asian Literature. However, the experimental group had additional reasons for their preference: (1) the method fostered teamwork and cooperation, and (2) it provided opportunities for participation in group activities.

Discussion

Based on the study's findings, Liang (2002) highlighted a significant distinction between cooperative learning and group learning. Cooperative learning emphasizes the achievement of better outcomes through collaboration and cooperation. Colorado (2007) echoed this sentiment, noting that cooperative learning is effective for all student types as it fosters respect and friendship among diverse groups. In contrast, Richards (2008), in his book *Communicative Language Teaching Today*, highlighted that traditional method ensure learning under the teacher's management and control. This was evident in the experimental study where respondents actively engaged in the learning process, unlike the control group respondents who passively received information. Kuzu (2008) explained that traditionally, teachers are seen as sources of knowledge while students are passive recipients.

Johnson, D. and Johnson, R. (2003) identified five key elements in cooperative learning: positive interdependence, individual accountability, quality group processing, clear teaching of group skills, and social skills instruction. The study confirmed that these roles and elements in the experimental group contributed differently to the discussion's success. For instance, while experimental group members had varied roles enhancing their contributions, control group members, being listeners and information receivers, found it easier to understand the subject and respond to the teacher.

Liang (2002) further emphasized that effective learning in cooperative settings is driven by collaboration. Liao (2009) also noted that cooperative learning aids cognitive development through group discussions, providing opportunities for explanation, logical reasoning, and debate. This approach helps solidify students' understanding of reading materials. Conversely, in the control group, traditional lecture methods were effective, particularly in honing listening skills. Hwang & Embi (2007) supported this by indicating that literature teaching in a cultural model uses a teacher-centered approach, ensuring the transfer of knowledge from teacher to student.

The study also observed that technology, such as televisions, laptops, and PowerPoint presentations, benefited both groups. In interviews, respondents in the control group expressed a preference for the teacher to use visual aids, and for stories, they suggested incorporating moving pictures and animations to enhance understanding.

Liao (2009) highlighted that cooperative learning successfully aids the development of cognitive processes. Group discussions provide numerous opportunities for explanations, logical reasoning, and debates, which help improve students' understanding of reading materials and solidify ideas.

Both the experimental and control groups appreciated the teacher's method of teaching Filipino 9 – Asian Literature. However, the experimental group uniquely valued two aspects: (1) the development of teamwork and cooperation, and (2) participation in group activities. Slavin (1999) confirmed that cooperative learning is a form of small-group learning where students work together in a social environment to solve problems. Johnson & Johnson (1994) added that positive cooperation enhances each member's motivation and productivity, leading to group success.

This study reveals that no single method is effective for all lessons. Cooperative learning is suitable for specific lessons like short stories and plays, while the lecture method is better for poems and essays. Cooperative learning is effective for narrative and prose content, and lectures are beneficial for interpreting poetic content.

Aziz's (2010) study using the Learning Together model and a quasi-experimental design showed significant positive effects of cooperative learning on Mathematics performance, with the experimental group showing greater improvement than the control group.

Conclusion

Experimental Group Performance

The highest scores in the pre-test and post-test of each lesson for the experimental group were achieved in the final test, specifically in lesson 2 (Novel of Saudi Arabia) and lesson 5 (Play of the Philippines). The lowest scores were in lesson 1 (Short Story of Singapore) and lesson 4 (Essay of Indonesia), recorded during the preliminary exam. Notably, scores in the preliminary exam were significantly lower than those in the final exam. Overall, the mean scores of the experimental group were higher in the final exam compared to the pre-test.

Control Group Performance

For the control group, the highest scores in the pre-test and post-test were also obtained in the final test, particularly in lesson 2 (Novel of Saudi Arabia). The lowest score was in lesson 2 (Novel of Saudi Arabia) during the pre-test. Scores in the pre-test were much lower compared to those in the post-test. The mean scores of the control group were higher in the post-test than in the pre-test.

Feedback on Teaching Methods

Respondents' feedback on the teaching methods used in Filipino 9 - Asian Literature revealed that the experimental group actively and enthusiastically participated in the learning process. In contrast, the control group mostly received information passively and their participation was minimal. The roles played by respondents varied; in the experimental group, respondents had different roles contributing to the discussion's success and effective learning, while in the control group, being listeners and information recorders facilitated easier understanding. Both teaching methods were effective, but differed in proficiency, with the experimental group sharing knowledge among peers, while the control group enhanced their listening skills. The use of technology such as television, laptops, and PowerPoint presentations benefited both groups.

According to interviews, control group respondents desired visual aids and animations for better comprehension of stories. The reasons why respondents from both groups favored the teaching method were similar, except for two aspects unique to the experimental group: (1) teamwork and cooperation development, and (2) participation in group activities.

Pre-Test Performance Comparison

The significant difference analysis between pre-test scores of the experimental and control groups indicated that three out of five lessons showed no significant difference, meaning the respondents' knowledge levels were similar before introducing the cooperative learning method and lectures.

Post-Test Performance Comparison

The post-test scores analysis showed a significant difference in three out of five lessons, suggesting that the cooperative learning method was not effective for all lessons. The lecture method was found to be more suitable for lessons such as lesson 3 (Poetry of the Philippines) and lesson 4 (Essay of Indonesia) for first-grade students.

Recommendations

In relation to the outcomes and conclusions of the study, the researcher humbly suggests the following recommendations:

1. Teachers should give a pre-test before starting the discussion to understand the prior knowledge of students and link it to the new knowledge gained. Teachers should examine the differences in students' scores between the pre-test and post-test to identify lessons that were not fully understood and conduct further discussions.
2. Filipino teachers should ensure that students are not just listeners or receivers of information. Allow students to be active participants during discussions to prevent boredom and increase interest in the Filipino subject. Teachers should maintain student interest in learning literature-related lessons to ensure lively participation during discussions and achieve positive results related to their class performance.
3. Teachers should ensure that the teaching materials used are not only to enhance teaching and facilitate learning but also give students the opportunity to handle, use, and manipulate the materials for an engaging experience.
4. Teachers should improve the use of cooperative learning and lecture methods in teaching Filipino poems, essays from Indonesia and Taiwan, and Japanese Tanka and Haiku. Ensure that cooperative learning fosters teamwork and cooperation, and encourages participation in discussions.
5. Teachers should diversify their teaching strategies and ensure they are based on the lesson and the students. Utilize other strategies and suggested activities from the Asian Literature workbook.
6. Allow students to be involved in the learning process and ensure they achieve valuable literacy, which is the primary goal of the Filipino curriculum in the K to 12 Program.
7. Use cooperative learning methods for selected lessons such as Short Story from Singapore, Novel from Saudi Arabia, and Play from the Philippines and Mongolia. When examining the content and form of these lessons, they are similar in prose form, where the content can easily be related to the students' lives and allows for creative thinking. Therefore, when conducting activities, they can quickly generate ideas or an output.
8. Use the lecture method for selected lessons in poetic form, such as Poems from the Philippines, Tanka and Haiku from Japan, and Essays from Indonesia and Taiwan. These lessons require extensive input from the teacher and extended listening time for the students due to the complex nature of the content and its deep meaning. The teacher needs to be active in this method to ensure full understanding of the lesson. The progress of students' learning should be assessed through teacher-administered tests. The effectiveness of using different methods, whether modern or traditional, depends on the lesson and the students.
9. Conduct a related study to test the effectiveness of modern (cooperative learning) and traditional (lecture) methods in teaching other subjects.
10. Conduct a related study where both groups of respondent experience both methods: modern (cooperative learning) and traditional (lecture), to better determine their effectiveness. Different strategies under cooperative learning may be used instead of Ask Together-Learn Together.

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